

Self-Esteem Impacts on Academic Performance of Students in the Public Sector in Erbil, Iraq

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Abstract:- In the humanities and psychology sciences, self-esteem indicates an individual's general personal emotional assessment of their value. It is an evaluation of the attitude of someone regarding somebody else. However, it was a crucial point to figure out how these elements form student self-esteem. The specific objectives of this research tried to explore the impacts of self-esteem on scholarly school students in Erbil, Iraq. The targeted sample size of the study is 186 students who have been selected randomly. Data were gained from school elements and students' emotions and outlooks regarding their self-esteem and academic show. Descriptive statistics and Chi-square tests have been used to analyze the collected data. The results showed that the teachers, time, good grades, peers, parents, and positive self-esteem impact academic performance and self-esteem.

Keywords:- Teachers' perception, Self-esteem, Academic achievements of students, Kurdistan Region.

I. INTRODUCTION

Throughout history, self-esteem as an idea initiated by famous scholars in social science was among the initial concepts (Thayer, 1970). Scholars hypothesized that self-esteem is a fit reason for an individual's success, separated from their assertions. The personal respect of a person would be educationally gained, which is distinguished by how they think. To build the complete personal care of someone, a person demands to supply achievements or lessen wishes for attainments. This keeps affecting the comprehension of personal esteem (Wickline, 2003). The famous self-psychologist (Walster, 1965) was worried about the essence of the unique background of the individual's acknowledgment of their skill. Leary (1999) trusted that every individual builds their unique perspective of actuality through the innovations themselves. Campbell (1991) recommended developing an understanding of self-maintaining improvement education lines. He distinguished seven distinct features of personal respect. Nonetheless, self-esteem is the third advancement phase of the scheme. It is the sentiment of dignity outcomes when the tyke achieves things on the tyke's accomplishment in undertakings (Baumeister and Boden, 1996). In 1979, Rosenberg researched immature self-respect and thought of three arrangements of self-respect: the surviving self, the desired self, and introducing self (Baumeister and Leary, 2000). To him, self-esteem is a more significant amount full of the feeling of adequacy. Self-assurance may add to self-esteem, but the two are synonymous. According to Harter (1993), students' numerical operations with the self followed at the

peak of educational success. The supremacy might come through socio-perception progress like globalization of social thoughts and comparisons. Evaluating students' confidence by their study level, the outcomes presented that students in high grades had higher self-confidence. Students' awareness of the different self-concept features increases as they improve during the time and grade levels (Pyszczynski and Solomon, 1991). A conceivable clarification was that pupils develop verbal and problem-solving knowledge as they take more educational topics in school (Bergami and Bagozzi, 2000).

The goal of this research is to figure out how school elements such as school atmosphere, lecturers, peers, and home elements like parents and lifestyle, parent-adolescent linkage, and demographic components such as age, fellow influence, gender, and equal statuses affect the students' self-respect concerning their educational performance. The primary aim of the research was to evaluate how self-respect interface with elements such as school atmosphere, teachers, fellows, and demographic factors such as age and gender, in the company of others influences students' performance.

II. METHODOLOGY

To get the critical information from the research, a questionnaire review has been generated mainly for goals collected from the teachers of the province (Erbil in Iraq) during 2017. Along these lines, the sample for the study consisted of 186 students. However, questionnaires were generated by the scientist to answer—section A comprised of shut-ended questions. Segments B and C used an organized three-point justified Likert-scale series of No (1), Maybe (2), and Yes (3) in line with Aydin and Kilic (2013). The answerers have been asked to request expand to which they accept/oppose with diverse expressions. Data gathered by monitoring the investigation equipment were assessed in line with each investigation question and hypothesis. Descriptive statistics (such as frequencies and percentages) were utilized to respond to the survey questions. The Chi-square test was used to examine the notions. To analyze everyone's responses, the SPSS was used.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The finding classification of the respondent by gender represented that 59.7% were male, while the remaining 40.3% were female. The result of marital status portrayed that nearly 51.1% of the teachers are married, and 48.9% are single. Also, according to the development, in the present research, 64.0% of the teachers have degrees of bachelor's, 28.0% have master and 8.1% have degrees of Ph.D. This can be explained due to the post requirements of education, as some posts require a bachelor's degree, other higher posts

require a bachelor's degree, and most top teacher posts require a postgraduate certificate. An illustrated this result improves the sincerity of data since most students are educated, and they were highly aware of the statements in the questionnaire. Table 1 explains that 11.3% of the respondents are less than 16 years old, and 36.0% are more than 18 years old. This variety of sample age serves the objectives of the study. More than that, it shows the long history of the organization and the continual process of hiring new teachers for individual posts.

Variables		Frequency	%	Mean	SD
Gender	Male	111	59.7	1.40	0.492
	Female	75	40.3		
Marital status of teachers	Single	91	48.9	1.51	0.501
	Married	95	51.1		
Teacher Education	Bachelor	119	64.0	1.44	0.640
	Master	52	28.0		
	PhD	15	8.1		
Students age's	<16	21	11.3	2.25	0.664
	17	98	52.7		
	>18	67	36.0		

Table 1: Classification Table by Social Demographic Variables Factors

Descriptive statistics were conducted to demonstrate respondents' self-esteem elements to assemble the mean and standard deviation for each factor. As shown in Table 2, 50.0% of students do not study on their own, 34.4% sometimes, and 15.6% study on their own. In addition, 12.9% of the students don't finish their assignments in time, while 51.1% finish them in time. When consulting their teachers for illumination on any difficult topic, 41.4% of students consult their teachers, and 16.7% do not (Table 2). As well as, 11.8% of the students chose no and increased to 48.4% yes about 'positive self-esteem has high academic performance. Lookingto Table 2, 10.2% of the students feel worthless when teachers don't appreciate their work, which increased to 48.9%. According to Table 2, 33.9% of the

students feel like showing it to others whenever they get good grades, and 18.8% do not feel better. Besides that, 10.8% of the students chose no and decreased to 50.0% yes on the term 'I have as many friends as people of my age. Further, 17.2% of the students selected no and decreased to 43.6% yes about 'Do peers have a relationship with self-esteem.' Therefore, the students have criticized health services and the workplace. In the term 'Do you emphasize your strengths,' 23.7% of students said no, 37.1% maybe, and 39.2% said yes (Table 2). Moreover, 30.6% of the students chose no and increased to 31.2% yes about 'Other people wish that they were like me. Also, 14.0% of the students selected no and increased to 55.9% yes about 'My parents are proud of the kind of person I am.

Variables		Frequency	%	Mean	Standard Deviation
Do you study on your own ?	No	93	50.0	1.66	0.735
	Maybe	64	34.4		
	Yes	29	15.6		
Do you complete your assignment in time ?	No	24	12.9	2.38	0.705
	Maybe	67	36.0		
	Yes	95	51.1		
Do you consult your teachers for clarification on any difficult topic?	No	31	16.7	2.25	0.723
	Maybe	78	41.9		
	Yes	77	41.4		
positive self-esteem has high academic performance	No	22	11.8	2.37	0.686
	Maybe	74	39.8		
	Yes	90	48.4		
Do you feel worthless when teachers don't appreciate your work?	No	19	10.2	2.39	0.666
	Maybe	76	40.9		
	Yes	91	48.9		
Whenever I get good grades , I feel like showing it to others	No	35	18.8	2.15	0.712
	Maybe	88	47.3		
	Yes	63	33.9		
I have as many friends as people of my age	No	20	10.8	2.39	0.675
	Maybe	73	39.2		
	Yes	93	50.0		
Do peers have a relationship with self-esteem	No	32	17.2	2.26	0.736
	Maybe	73	39.2		
	Yes	81	43.6		
Do you emphasize your strengths?	No	44	23.7	2.16	0.718
	Maybe	69	37.1		
	Yes	73	39.2		
Other people wish that they were like me	No	57	30.6	2.01	0.788
	Maybe	71	38.2		
	Yes	58	31.2		
My parents are proud of the kind of person I am	No	26	14.0	2.42	0.725
	Maybe	56	30.1		
	Yes	104	55.9		

Table 2: Self-esteem and academic performance

The relationship between student characteristics indicates a statistically significant connection between 'self-esteem and the educational show' (Table 3). The outcomes reveal a statistically significant linkage between 'Do you consult your teachers for clarification in any difficult topic' and 'self-esteem and academic performance' ($X^2 = 16.874$; $p: 0.002$). According to a result, 39.5% of the respondents chose no about teachers and increased to 41.4% satisfied with the term self-esteem.

The significant association between 'Do peers have a relationship with self-esteem' and 'self-esteem and academic performance' ($X^2 = 24.415$; $p: 0.000$). The majority of respondents (47.1%) selected maybe on the term of the mission and increased to 55.2% satisfied with self-esteem.

A significant relationship was observed between 'Whenever I get good grades, I feel like showing it to others' and 'self-esteem and academic performance' ($X^2 = 14.060$; $p: 0.007$). The highest percentage of respondents

(38.8%) may be about good grades and decreased to 37.2% satisfied with self-esteem.

There is a significant association between 'positive self-respect has high educational show' and 'self-esteem and the academic performance' ($X^2 = 28.655$; $p: 0.000$). On the other hand, the results represent that a combined 62.1% of respondents chose yes in the row of positive self-esteem and decreased to 40.0% satisfied with self-esteem.

Further, the results represented that the relationship between 'My parents are proud of the kind of person I am and 'self-esteem and academic performance' ($X^2 = 11.705$; $p = 0.020$) is significant. Moreover, nearly 43.5% of the employees selected maybe about parents and decreased to 9.3% satisfied with the term self-esteem.

Also, the relationship is significant between 'Do you complete your assignment in time' and 'self-esteem and the academic performance' ($X^2 = 13.848$; $p: 0.008$). The results

indicate that 48.2% of respondents chose it may be about time, decreasing to 25.9% satisfied with self-esteem.

Variables		Self-esteem				χ^2	P-value
		Not satisfied	Somewhat Satisfied	Satisfied	Total (%)		
Teachers	No	39.5	34.9	25.6	100.0	16.874	0.002
	Maybe	12.9	54.2	32.9	100.0		
	Yes	12.0	46.6	41.4	100.0		
Peers	No	32.6	27.9	39.5	100.0	24.415	0.000
	Maybe	4.7	47.1	48.2	100.0		
	Yes	6.9	37.9	55.2	100.0		
good grades	No	30.2	32.6	37.2	100.0	14.060	0.007
	Maybe	8.3	52.9	38.8	100.0		
	Yes	19.0	32.8	48.2	100.0		
positive self-esteem	No	34.9	37.2	27.9	100.0	28.655	0.000
	Maybe	4.7	40.0	55.3	100.0		
	Yes	8.6	29.3	62.1	100.0		
Parents	No	67.4	23.3	9.3	100.0	11.705	0.020
	Maybe	43.5	43.5	13.0	100.0		
	Yes	46.6	29.3	24.1	100.0		
Time	No	46.5	30.2	23.3	100.0	13.848	0.008
	Maybe	25.9	48.2	25.9	100.0		
	Yes	25.9	29.3	44.8	100.0		

Table 3: Association between Self-esteem and the academic performance

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The accompanying conclusions have been drawn concerning the set objectives from the discoveries. However, people's self-esteem appears to interact with their educational show positively or negatively. A person whose self-esteem is perceived endeavors tough to attain academic superiority. According to the discoverers, pupils counted as necessary by their parents felt inspired to study and signified a glorious future. These kinds of students made their family and particularly their teachers proud. The pupils, in turn, identified their attempts by giving encouragement and rewards. Students with ineffective performance indicated despair symptoms and believed they could not achieve good marks even though they worked hard.

Sentiments of ability, pleasing frankness, and belief influence students' activity. Students who felt commendable before their mentors and parents had their aims designed to fulfill the demands of a bright future. The discoveries uncovered that these kinds of students influence the group conversation, do their assignments, and do not hesitate to consult their teacher to clarify in spaces that challenge them. Afterward, students who performed or inutility never completed their homework on time on most occasions. They always think that they are useless and others do not like them.

According to the outcomes, there are some recommendations: The atmosphere of the school is vital for promoting students to improve students' self-esteem. Therefore, teachers should encourage learners to participate in curricular and co-curricular actions to raise their self-confidence. However, teachers should lead and give consultations to students repeatedly to avoid a phrase of despair. Most students with no capability of class activities have not seen a force to adapt and expand a stereotype thinking, whereas they tried hard but could not get good grades. On the other hand, parents should always motivate their children by appreciating their work at school and encouraging a brighter future.

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